

UKRAINE' LABOR POTENTIAL: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF COMPETITIVE FUNCTIONING

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Abstract

The efficiency of labor potential' reproduction and use is one of the key factors of competitive businesses' management, socium progress and social harmony in the conditions of neo- and post-industrial economic modes that have been spreading throughout the world and its macro-regions. The organization, regulation priorities of labor potential' reproductive environment and employment sphere, trends and problems of their functioning determine a multiplicative cluster of incentives and disincentives for the life quality in Ukraine in a number of its manifestations, among which, in particular, – the characteristics of the living environment (household, work), resource base, indicators and features of human resources' reproduction and use that are of great importance for recovering from war losses and damages in Ukraine' post-war realities against the backstage of modern competitive globalized world. Socially recognized practice and already achieved parameters of the life quality and labor potential reproduction outline the long term material and immaterial incentives and motivators of individual and community human development, parameters and processes of diversification of the national economy' and the labor market' territorial segments, and therefore – the expectations and sustainability of positive post-war socio-economic and, among other, demographic, professional and qualification, migration shifts.

Keywords: labor potential, workforce, employment sphere, competitiveness, Ukraine' socio-economic policy.

Introduction. The efficiency of labor potential' reproduction and use is one of the key factors of competitive businesses' management, socium progress and social harmony in the conditions of neo- and post-industrial economic modes that have been spreading throughout the world and its macro-regions at the same time with intensification of communications' spectrum (including cross-border logistics), globalization of living practices' set of compact human communities (up to the level of separate state entities and their political associations). The principles and priorities of labor potential' reproduction and use, the sequence of relevant long-term guidelines serve as the basis for the reproduction and improvement of the level and quality of life of the entire population, i.e. factors that (along with systematic national policy of innovative modernization, economic diversification, socium solidarity, including by social protection' means) will provide a powerful reverse influence on the sustainable competitive development' rate of post-war Ukraine against the modern background of the world further globalization.

The organization (mechanisms, tools), regulation priorities of labor potential' reproductive environment and employment sphere, trends and problems of their functioning determine a multiplicative cluster of incentives and disincentives for the life quality in Ukraine and other countries all over the world in a number of its manifestations, among which, in particular, – the characteristics of the living environment (household, work), resource base, indicators and features of human resources' reproduction and use that are also of great importance for recovering from war losses and damages in Ukrainian post-war realities.

It's worth to mention generalized key factors of the orientation and quality of the processes of formation

and improvement of the living standard and living environment, reproduction and use of human resources and, in particular, labor potential, such as:

- aggregate (direct and indirect) expenses for the workforce reproduction – financial, other material – in the prime cost and the market value of production of each economic activity, especially in the specialization branches in the national and foreign markets;

- legislatively regulated potential and realities of local budgets' practice regarding the accumulation of business entities' taxes in the locations of their production base and economic activity;

- mechanisms of distribution and redistribution of budget and other targeted funds in practices of social protection, individual and community human capital' increasing, activation of the population' employment and entrepreneurial initiatives.

Brief literature review. The problems, peculiarities, mechanisms of national labor potential' use and reproduction in the context of the favorable implementation of systemic socio-economic challenges, mitigation and overcome of the current period' threats, expectations of Ukraine' competitive post-war revival are highlighted in works, where:

- methodological principles of human capital' and employment potential' use, social institutions of their organization in the realities of the national market economy in the globalized world have being developed [1–3];

- positive and negative trends in the employment sphere' functioning, national and territorial practices of reproduction and improvement of the efficiency of the labor potential' use in the near pre-war period, as well as in the conditions of nowadays military operations and delayed negative consequences of martial law period have being determined [4–6];

– approaches to increasing the strategy' and policy' effectiveness of the population' productive employment, including on the basis of modernization of the market infrastructure, balancing the supply of labor and demand for it, improving the competitiveness of its professional and qualification characteristics at the individual and community levels, have been substantiated [7–9].

At the same time, its worth to carry out further identification of the problems that will have the most acute impact on the competitiveness of the national labor potential and economy, as well as the population' productive employment at the stages of Ukraine' post-war stabilization and further development.

The purpose of the article is to determine the problems and priorities of Ukraine' labor potential use and reproduction in the conditions of socio-economic development' challenges and threats to the employment sphere' functioning, which will remain relevant at various stages of the post-war revival, taking into account their influence on the realization of the national economy' competitiveness factors in the globalized world (and precisely the needs for: diversifying the economic complex and its territorial subsystems; accelerated developing and clustering of innovative and knowledge-intensive activities; raising and implementing standards of productive employment, decent work and life quality).

Main results. Most generally, on the one hand, the competitive functioning of Ukrainian labor potential implies the diversified employment sphere, the components of which (branches, business entities) are competitive on the national and foreign markets, so they can offer and guarantee decent wages. On the other hand, this phenomenon is based on the quality socium environment of work and non-work (household, public) life activities, which stimulates and promotes reproduction and improvement of individual and community professional and qualification potential. Such conditions actualize the consistent diversification of the national economic complex and its territorial subsystems towards the accelerated development of innovative and science-intensive activities (in particular, with a funds' fast turnover, attractive for entrepreneurship). The forecast made in 2023 by the Ministry of Economy also serves as an argument for the urgent need to diversify economy' structure and competitive specialization, because it noted the necessity to engage at least 4.5 million employees on the Ukraine' labor market over the next ten years [10].

Large-scale military actions force us to expect catastrophic losses of the economically active population, because, according to the United Nations Organization, 6.3 million Ukrainian refugees were registered in the countries all over the world in 2023; according to expert calculations, there were about 3.7 – 4.8 million people in European countries. At least half of the forced migrants were children, and most of the adults were women aged 25–49. From 40 to 60% of migrants may remain abroad, as the propensity to return (primarily among families with children, young people) significantly decreases over time [10]. According to the most

balanced assessments (in our opinion), due to the consequences and results of military operations and expected irreversible migration Ukraine will loss up to 23-32% of the working population [11–13].

According to the analysis of vacancies that employers submitted to the State Employment Service, the most sought after in mid-2023 were: skilled workers with tools – 21%; workers for maintaining, operating equipment and machines – 16%; workers in the sphere of trade and services – 15% [14]. However, the average salary in these vacancies was only UAH 11,000. Therefore, employers are not ready to finance their own need for qualified workers (even of a rather narrow specialization). Thus, according to the Construction Industry Trade Union, the salary of crane operators and construction workers is very low – nowadays such workers can rarely earn more than UAH 20,000, even with the salary' unofficial part [15]. As of 2023, the experts of the Construction Industry Trade Union estimated a decent wage for work, which also guarantees its safety for the employed, in the amount of UAH 200 per hour.

The currently widespread non-tariff wage systems and corporate standards for evaluating the suitability of the employees' qualifications for the positions they hold and job duties' scope, which are weakly consistent with the relevant state standards, contribute to numerous manipulations with salaries' rates and enterprises' wage funds. The source of the problems is the vague regulation of non-tariff wage systems in national legislation, which allows employers to save on the wage fund at the employee' expense, while paying a united social contribution from the monthly minimum wage.

According to the letter of the Ministry of Social Policy dated March 20, 2017 No. 766/0/101-17/28, the state guarantee that must be observed for workers with hourly payment is the minimum wage in an hourly (not monthly) amount. Therefore, if an employee (whom hourly rate is set or whose work is paid according to the qualification characteristics and certain work results determined by the employer) has fulfilled the monthly labor rate, but the accrued salary amount turned out to be less than the minimum monthly salary, then no additional payment is made to it. In turn, in accordance with subsection 2 of part 5 of article 8 of the Law «On the collection and accounting of united contribution to mandatory state social insurance» dated 07/08/2010 No. 2464, as well as with the clarification of the State Fiscal Service dated 04/13/2018 No. 1549/IPK/15-32-13-01-10, the monthly salary may be less than the monthly minimum wage, without requiring the employer to pay the difference. At the same time, only the mandatory deduction of the united social contribution is controlled.

A significant role in the accumulation and aggravation of the problems of the employment sphere' functioning, which affect the situation and prospects of domestic demographic and migration processes, is played by the government' orientation to the consistent reduction of trade unions' role, downsizing the spread of collective-contractual regulation of employment and working conditions.

On the conviction of the regional associations of Ukrainian trade unions, in particular, expressed as early

as 2021, the course to implementing neoliberal policies in the economy and social sphere, weakening the state's regulatory function that was taken by the authorities, as well as an effective social dialogue's lack (especially in establishing of a range of significant social minimums) leads to deepening of labor results' unfair distribution and poverty' growth, destabilization of demand and supply in the labor market, further labor migration increase and aggravation of social confrontation in the country [16]. With the government help, a significant part of business avoids collective bargaining, which negatively affects the observance of citizens' labor, social and economic rights.

The number of collective agreements concluded and registered in Ukraine in 2010-2015 decreased by 27.6% (from 105 thousand to 76 thousand), in 2010-2017 – by 39.7% (to 63.4 thousand), in 2010-2021 – by 58.9% (to almost 43.2 thousand) [17; 18]. At the end of 2021, 5064.4 thousand or 70.2% of full-time employees were covered by collective agreements [18].

According to sociological studies of the social dialogue' parameters on the compliance of employment with the decent work criteria, conducted in a number of settlements and regions, the lowest level of collective agreement regulation was registered among workers in such types of economic activities as temporary accommodation and organization of meals, wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles, real estate transactions [17]. At the same time, the level of collective bargaining was high in industry, financial and insurance activities, arts, sports, entertainment and recreation. The fulfillment level of the collective agreements' provisions, according to the employees' assessment, is also heterogeneous. Its highest indicators were observed in professional, scientific and technical activities, while the worst – in education and real estate transactions [17].

The privatization processes and other forms of state-owned enterprises' reorganization, which are carried out in order to fill the state budget, have revealed a number of acute problems of observing the social and labor rights of their collectives that affect the preservation of the professional and qualification potential of industries and the economy in general. According to the assessment of Mechanical Engineering and Instrument Engineering trade union, one of the main problems is the maximum retention of highly qualified employees, ensuring their protection and compliance with labor legislation in the reorganization process [19].

Branch trade unions also often note significant contradictions between the parameters of the labor legislation' adaptation of Ukraine and European Union, the implementation of international norms of labor organization and safety, as well as realities of the national practice of the employment sphere' reforming. In particular, specialists of the trade union of agro-industrial complex' employees and the trade union IUF international organization found contradictions between a number of documents ratified by Ukraine (International Labor Organization' Conventions No. 129 on labor inspection in agriculture, No. 135 on the protection of the rights of workers' representatives at the enterprise and

the opportunities that provided to them, No. 155 on occupational safety and hygiene and the production environment, No. 184 on occupational safety and hygiene in agriculture) and the draft law «On the safety and health of workers at work» developed by the Ministry of Economy [20]. The trade union community believes that this draft law carries the risk of destroying the system of institutions of national legislation, narrows the rights and guarantees of workers for healthy occupational conditions. First of all, they are talking about risks in the workplace, the safety and health of women workers in agriculture, ensuring the special needs of women in connection with pregnancy, breastfeeding and reproductive health [20].

The Law «On amendments to certain legislative acts on simplifying the labor relations' regulation in the field of small and medium-sized entrepreneurship and reducing the administrative burden on entrepreneurial activity», which was adopted on 07/19/2022, according to the conclusion of the Professional Unions' Federation, significantly limits fundamental constitutional labor rights and guarantees of hundreds of thousands of workers in this category and puts them in unequal conditions with others, as it introduces extreme forms of labor relations' liberalization and discrimination regarding the rights of workers who work at enterprises with up to 250 employees [21].

According to the experts' conclusions, the provisions of this Law contradict the Constitution of Ukraine, ILO Conventions, EU Directives and in practice will lead to the deterioration of the employment contract conditions for hired personnel in comparison to the current legislation due to the unfavorable conditions' imposition in the individual employment contract, employees' discrimination and the weakening of the rights-protecting role of trade unions, as well as their legal representatives. The result of this law implementation will be the destruction of the interests' balance between the employment contract' parties and the formalization of opportunities for the employer absolute dictation in relation to the employee [21].

The 111th International Labor Conference emphasized the need for systematic coordination of political actions at the international, regional and national levels with social issues, since only such a strategy will allow to resist growing economic inequality (in particular, in dimensions of: citizens' deprivation from social protection; wages below subsistence minimum; tendencies towards bankruptcy of micro- and small enterprises; gender inequality in wages, when women on average earn up to 20% less than their male colleagues) [22]. For reference, it should be noted that in the first half of 2023 in Ukraine, men's wages were higher than women's by almost 19% [23]. The ILO announced the following priorities:

- ensuring a balanced consideration of environmental, economic and social aspects, in particular, during the international financial system' restructuring;
- conducting a coordinated policy on issues of social protection and decent work and increasing investments in this sphere [22].

In addition to the current extremely acute security threats, their immediate and long-term consequences

for the quantitative and qualitative parameters of the labor force and employment, Ukraine (so as the whole world) will face numerous new economic and social challenges in the near future. Their content is associated with overcoming the economic recession' consequences, the national markets' further globalization, at the same time as the segmentation of sectoral foreign markets, the digitalization of work, the transition to new professional standards based on a modernized national classifier. As a result, we should expect the reduction of jobs in the economy' traditional sectors, the large-scale spread of employment non-standard forms, which, among other, will lead to a decrease in trade union membership and the limitation of trade union mechanisms for the hired labor protection [16].

According to expert estimates, over the next 5 years 83 million jobs will be lost and 69 million new ones will be created on the world labor market, which will lead to the elimination of 17% of jobs at least [24]. In general, administrative positions and jobs in the spheres of security and trade are at risk of the biggest reductions. Cashiers, accountants, administrators, secretaries and a number of other workers may be out of a job due to the expectations of automation and digitization of some processes. Among these workers we should also mention: security guards; household workers; collectors and factory workers; postal service employees; bank cashiers; shop assistants; telemarketing specialists; customer service personnel; managers of business services and administration; door-to-door salesmen (in fields), street vendors, as well as related workers. Workers with basic education and women are also expected to face significant challenges, as employers would look for experienced professionals and men for labor vacancies [24].

The forecasted world trends, while multiplying by an outdated structure, unsatisfactory diversification, significant resource-raw material and logistics-transport specialization of the national economy and its territorial subsystems, may have a sharp impact on the Ukrainian labor potential and employment sphere, especially if we compare them with the modern demand dynamics on the labor market.

According to the recruitment management system Work.ua [25], sales consultant, sales manager, driver, cook and accountant were consistently dominated among the five most in-demand positions in the summer of 2023. In turn, the largest increase in June 2023 was shown only by the seasonally significant small group of primary school teacher vacancies (+44%, in absolute terms – approximately from 2.3 to 5.9% of the total demand for the above-mentioned most sought-after positions), which is related to the search of private schools and kindergartens for temporary staff in order to prepare children for school during the summer vacations.

In October 2023, the most part of vacancies were offered in the following categories: «Working specialties, production» (+2% increase by September 2023, 20,018 vacancies); «Sphere of services» (19,417 job offers, 4% less than in September); «Sales, purchases» (+2%, 14,012); «Retail trade» (-1%, 12,755); «Logistics, warehousing, foreign economic activities»

(+3%, 11,265); «Hotel and restaurant business, tourism» (-7%, 10,518); «Medicine, pharmaceuticals» (6,583 vacancies, -1% by September) [26]. According to the level of demand increase for workers, it was most noticeable in insurance (+7%, 205 job vacancies), sphere of security and safety (+5%, 2164), real estate operations (+5%, 767), jurisprudence (+4%, 1,245); finance and banking (+3%, 4,300 vacancies). Among the positions, the greatest growth was shown by the demand for tire fitting masters (+23% by September), couriers (+22%), crane operators (+17%), furniture designers (+14%), media buyers (+14%), stackers, packaging workers (+12%), office managers (+10%), sales coordinators (+10%) [26].

Therefore, the long-term orientations of changes in the labor potential and labor market, related to the national economy' innovative modernization, as well as the increase of the share of highly qualified workers and specialists for the specialization branches in the employment structure, are still not traced.

Conclusions. We should outline the range of problems that will have the most noticeable impact on the significant aspects of the labor force use and reproduction at the stages of Ukraine' post-war stabilization and further development due to reducing the competitiveness of the national human capital and the economy in general, complicating the economic complex' diversification, the professional and qualification potential' improvement, the population' productive employment provision, as well as implementation of decent work', work and non-work life quality' standards. First of all they include:

- unsystematic and unsatisfactory consequence of the national policy for harmonizing economic, foreign economic and social issues towards combating economic inequality and low efficiency of social protection;

- inconsistency of minimum wage guarantees with socially acceptable living standards, which generalize physiological and social subsistence minimums;

- the widespread practice of misbalance between offered salary, on the one hand, and complexity of performed work, as well as demand on certain specialties and specializations in the labor market (in particular, on workers with tools, workers for maintaining, operating equipment and machines, engineering and technical specialists), on the other hand;

- manipulative practices of savings on the wage fund due to unsatisfactory control over the justification of non-tariff wage systems, as well as corporate standards for assessing the suitability of the employees' qualifications for the positions they hold and the scope of their job duties;

- deterioration of the regulatory and legal provision of a number of employees' social and labor rights under the pretext of reforming labor legislation, in particular, in accordance with the requirements of the Association Agreement with the EU, as well as external creditors;

- reduction of the scope of collective bargaining regulation of employment and labor conditions, especially at enterprises with up to 250 employees; the con-

sistent removal of trade unions from effective mechanisms for defending decent work standards;

– the inevitable transformation of national and macro-regional labor markets under the influence of: the need for overcoming the world's economic recession consequences; further globalization of goods and services markets at the same time as competition's increase in sectors of internal markets; labor digitization; modernization of professional and qualification standards against the backstage of innovative activities' and their clusters' diversification; contradictory trends in the spread of employment' non-standard forms and the consequent complication of practices and mechanisms for hired labor' protection.

The sustainability and public recognition of comfortable quantitative and qualitative parameters of household and work life play a key role in improving the labor potential' professional and qualification parameters, initiating and implementing incentives for diversifying the employment sphere and territorial labor markets, expanding the country' foreign economic specialization, increasing the national producer competitiveness in clusters of modern technological modes' branches (neo-, post-industrial).

The life quality of employees and their family members is based on:

– the consistency of mechanisms for guaranteeing decent wages, social protection and activation of economic and educational initiatives of the working and pre-working age population, which ensure the sufficiency of labor income and redistributed resources of social protection for the natural, professional and qualification reproduction of the labor potential, workforce' labor and social mobility, stimulation of vulnerable categories' range, progressive pension provision;

– the comfort of socio-cultural and socio-political conditions and country' development trends for the spectrum of ethno-religious communities that inhabit it, including the viability of values and guidelines for the consolidation and evolution of the macro-social system;

– the quality of the environment' natural and anthropogenic components, their balance and ergonomics in the context of the sustainable development principles.

These factors, while potentiating by established socially recognized practice and already achieved parameters of the life quality, in the Ukrainian post-war realities will outline the long term material and immaterial incentives and motivators of individual and community human development, parameters and processes of diversification of the national economy' and the labor market' territorial segments, and therefore – the expectations and sustainability of positive socio-economic and, among other, demographic professional and qualification, migration shifts.

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